

The Proximate Analysis, Vitamin Constituents, Phytochemical Screening and Antioxidant Potentials of Aqueous and Ethanol Root Extracts of *Chrysophyllum albidum* (African Star Apple)

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Abstract

Over the decades, medicinal plant research has established the vast nutritive and therapeutic effects of phytochemicals used in the treatment of different diseases. This study is aimed at evaluating the proximate analysis, vitamin constituents, phytochemical screening and antioxidant potentials aqueous and ethanol root extracts of *Chrysophyllum albidum*. All assays were carried out using standard protocols. The results from the proximate analysis and vitamin content showed that the root contained high amount of carbohydrate (24.06 ± 2.14 mg/g) and fibre (30.90 ± 2.62 mg/g) while the vitamin analysis showed that vitamin C (0.018 mg/g) and vitamin E (0.09 mg/g) are present. The results of the phytochemical screening of both extracts revealed the presence of saponins, flavonoids, alkaloids, phenols, terpenoids, xanthoprotein, carbohydrate and tannins. Quinone, cardiac glycoside and oxalate were detected in the aqueous extract only. Steroid was below detectable level in both extracts. Ethanol extract showed significantly higher ($P < 0.05$) reducing power (1.369 ± 0.09 nm) and total antioxidant capacity (165 ± 5 mg AAE/g Extract) when compared to aqueous extract at 0.855 ± 0.03 nm and 126.7 ± 16 mg AAE/g Extract respectively. There is no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) in the ferric reducing antioxidant potential and 1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) radical scavenging potential of both extracts. Our findings suggests that *Chrysophyllum albidum* root is a valuable source of bioactive compounds, with the high benefit that may be effective in the management of oxidative stress related diseases.

Keywords: Antioxidant, *Chrysophyllum albidum*, Minerals, Phytochemical, Proximate, Vitamins.

1.0 Introduction

Chrysophyllum albidum (*C. albidum*), commonly called white star apple or African star apple, belong to the family of Sapotaceae (which has up to 800 species) [1]. It is common throughout the tropical Central, East and West Africa regions and other parts of the world [2]. The fruit is seasonal (usually from the months of December to March). The plant is a crop of commercial value in Nigeria [3]. Local names of African star apple include azongogwe or azonbobwe in Benin, Utieagadava in Urhobo, agbalumo in Yoruba, udara in Ibo, Efik and Ibibio, ehya in Igala, agwaluma in Hausa tribes of Nigeria [4]. Ethno-medicinal values in folklore medicine are numerous. *Chrysophyllum albidum* bark is employed for the treatment of yellow fever and malaria [4]. The leaf is used as an emollient and for the treatment of stomachache

and diarrhoea. The leaf and cotyledons from its seed are used as ointments in the treatment of vaginal and dermatological infections in Western Nigeria [5]. The roots, barks and leaves of *C. albidum* are widely used as an application to sprains, bruises and wounds in southern Nigeria. The seeds and roots extracts of *C. albidum* is used to arrest bleeding from fresh wounds, and to inhibit microbial growth of known wound contaminants and also enhance wound healing process [6].

Phytochemical and nutrient composition study by Okoli and Okere [6] on the phytochemistry of *Chrysophyllum albidum* stem slash, seed cotyledon, leaves and root revealed the presence of alkaloids, tannins, phenols and flavonoids; except cardiac glycosides in the root; tannins in leaves; and phenol in seed. The study by

Ojemekele et al. [7] on the methanol leaf extracts of *C. albidum* also revealed the presence of flavonoids, phenols, saponins, steroids and alkaloids. MacDonald et al. [8] also revealed the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins and tannins in *Chrysophyllum albidum*. The fruit was found to have the highest content of ascorbic acid per 100 g of edible fruit, which is about 100 times that of oranges and 10 times of that of guava and cashew. *Chrysophyllum albidum* is also an excellent source of vitamins, irons and flavours to diets [9]. *C. albidum* methanol leaf extract has antioxidant properties by scavenging free radicals and decreasing lipid peroxidation according to Ojemekele et al. [7]. Adebayo and co-workers recommended that *Chrysophyllum albidum* could be employed as sources of natural antioxidant boosters for the treatment of free radical implicated oxidative stress disorders. Ethanol extract showed more scavenging activity of free radicals compared to the aqueous extract. Olorunnisola et al. [10] evaluated the antihyperglycemic and hypolipidemic effect of ethanol extract of *Chrysophyllum albidum* seed cotyledon in model of alloxan-induced diabetic rats and discovered that the daily treatment of diabetic rats with ethanol extract twice daily for 7 days significantly decreased ($p < 0.05$) after treatment of rats with the extract. The histopathological studies of the liver tissue of rats in the group treated with CCl_4 showed marked centrilobular fatty degeneration and necrosis while the groups treated with plant extract showed signs of protection against carbon tetrachloride as evidenced by the absence of necrosis. The anti-plasmodial, hematological, serum biochemical and pathological effects of *Chrysophyllum albidum* methanol bark extract were evaluated using Swiss albino male mice models. Adewoye et al., [11] showed that the methanol extract of *C. albidum* contains antiplasmodial substance(s) which help to reduce parasitaemia and hence the rate of erythrocyte destruction during infection [11]. There is paucity of information on the proximate, vitamin composition, phytochemical and antioxidant properties of the root extract of *Chrysophyllum albidum* hence this research.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Collection of plant

Plant of *C. albidum* was collected from a private farm in Benin City, Nigeria and authenticated in the Department of Plant Biology and Biotechnology, University of Benin where a

voucher specimen number UBH-C362 was deposited.

2.2 Preparation of plant material

The roots were washed and dried at room temperature in the laboratory. Dried root samples were pulverized and 250 g were soaked in 2.5 litres of distilled water and 2.5 litres of ethanol separately for 72 hours. The suspension was filtered and the filtrate was concentrated using a rotary evaporator and a freeze drier.

2.3 Proximate analysis

Crude fibre, crude protein, moisture, ether extract and moisture content were determined according to the official methods of the association of official analytical chemist [12]. and all samples were evaluated in triplicates.

2.4 Mineral analysis

Analysis of sodium, calcium, magnesium, iron, manganese, zinc, potassium and phosphorus were determined using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (Model NF-123D, Punjab, India) according to Association of Official Analytical Chemist [13].

2.5 Determination of vitamin C and E content

Vitamin C and vitamin E estimation were done according to the method of Sawicki et al.[14].

2.6 Phytochemical screening

The aqueous and ethanol extracts of *C. albidum* were used for phytochemical tests and to identify the constituents, standard procedures were carried out as described by Trease and Evans[15] and Sofowora [16]. Tannins, saponins, carbohydrate, terpenoides, flavonoids, cardiac glycosides, phenols, steroids, xanthoproteins, oxalate and quinones were estimated following standard methods [17].

2.7 Reducing power assay

The sample extracts of the plants were put in 1 ml of phosphate buffer in a test tube and 5 ml of 0.2 M phosphate buffer, pH 6.6, was added. To this, 5 ml of 1% potassium ferricyanide solution was added. The mixture was then incubated at 50 °C for 20 min. 5 ml of 10% TCA was added after the incubation and the content was centrifuged at 1000 rpm for 10 min. The upper layer of the

supernatant (5 ml) was mixed with 5 ml of distilled water. 1 ml of ferric chloride was then added and vortexed. Then, the absorbance of the reaction mixture was read spectrophotometrically at 700 nm against water blank [18].

2.8 Ferric reducing antioxidant power (FRAP) assay

The Ferric Reducing Antioxidant Power (FRAP) assay was carried out using a modified method of Benzie and Strain [19]. The FRAP solution was prepared as follows: 25 ml of 300 mM acetate buffer of pH 3.6 was mixed with 2.5 ml of 10mM 2,4,6-tripyridylstriaizine (TPTZ) in 40 mM HCl, and 2.5 ml of 20 mM ferric chloride ($\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$) solution. 1.5 ml of freshly prepared FRAP solution was added to 1ml of the extracts (1mg/ml). The reaction mixtures were incubated at 37°C for 30 min and the increase in absorbance at 593nm was measured. FeSO_4 was used for the calibration curve and ascorbic acid served as the positive control. FRAP values (expressed as mg Fe (II)/g of the extract) for the extracts were then extrapolated from the standard curve.

2.9 Estimation of diphenyl-2-picryl-hydrazyl (DPPH) radical scavenging activity

The free radical scavenging capacity of the plant extracts against 1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) radical was determined by a slightly modified method of Brand-Williams et al.[20]. Briefly, 0.5 ml of 0.3 mM DPPH solution in methanol was added to 2 ml of various concentrations (0.2 - 1.0 mg/ml) of the extracts. The reaction tubes were shaken and incubated for 15 min at room temperature in the dark, and the absorbance read at 517 nm. All tests were performed in triplicate. Vitamin C was used as standard control, with similar concentrations as the test samples prepared. A blank containing 0.5 ml of 0.3 mM DPPH and 2 ml methanol was prepared and treated as the test samples. The radical scavenging activity was calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{DPPH radical scavenging activity (\%)} = \frac{[A_0 - A_1]}{A_0} \times 100.$$

Where A_0 is the absorbance of DPPH radical + methanol; A_1 is the absorbance of DPPH radical + sample extract or standard.

2.10 Evaluation of total antioxidant capacity

This was done according to the method described by Prieto et al. [21]. To 1 ml of the samples, 1 ml of reagent (0.6 M sulfuric acid, 28 mM sodium phosphate and 4 mM ammonium molybdate) was added and then incubated at 95 ° C for 90 min. after the samples are cooled to room temperature, the absorbance were measured at 695 nm against a blank. A blank solution contained 1 ml of reagent solution and 1 ml of solvent. Total antioxidant capacity were expressed as equivalent of ascorbic acid.

2.11 Statistical Analysis

The analyses were done in triplicates and the data obtained were expressed as mean \pm standard error of the means (mean \pm S.E.M). The data were subjected to one way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and differences between samples were determined Duncan multiple range test. Significant was declared if $p \leq 0.05$.

3.0 Results and Discussion

Table 1: Proximate analysis of *C. albidum* root

Proximate Composition	Amount(mg/g)
Moisture content	41.80 \pm 1.05
Ash content	1.70 \pm 0.36
lipid	0.25 \pm 0.05
fibre	30.90 \pm 2.62
protein	1.20 \pm 0.16
carbohydrates	24.06 \pm 2.14

Values are mean \pm standard error of mean (n=3)

Table 2: Mineral analysis of *C. albidum* root

Elements	Amount (mg/g)
Sodium	0.30 \pm 0.04
Calcium	8.20 \pm 0.05
Magnesium	0.96 \pm 0.05
Iron	0.20 \pm 0.04
Manganese	0.35 \pm 0.05
Zinc	1.12 \pm 0.10
Potassium	13.50 \pm 0.55
Phosphorus	11.31 \pm 0.50

Values are mean \pm standard error of mean (n=3)

Table 3: Vitamin analysis of *C. albidum* root

Vitamins	Amount(mg/g)
C	0.018 \pm 0.005
E	0.090 \pm 0.0001

Values are mean \pm standard error of mean (n=3)

Table 4: Phytochemical constituents of aqueous and ethanol root extracts of *Chrysophyllum albidum*

Phytochemicals	Aqueous extract	Ethanol extract
Flavonoids	+	+
Phenols	++	++
Saponins	+	+++
Tannins	+	++
Terpenoids	+	+++
Xanthoproteins	+	+++
Carbohydrate	++	+++
Cardiac glycosides	+	-
Quinones	+	-
Oxalate	+	-

KEY : - absent , +: trace amounts, ++: moderate amount, +++: high amounts

Figure 1: Reducing power assessment of aqueous and ethanol root extracts of *Chrysophyllum albidum*. Values are expressed as mean \pm SEM, n = 3. Different lowercase letters represent significant difference between means at $p < 0.05$

Figure 2: Ferric acid reducing antioxidant potential (FRAP) assessment of aqueous and ethanol root extracts of *Chrysophyllum albidum*. Values are expressed as mean \pm SEM, n = 3. Different lowercase letters represent significant difference between means at $p < 0.05$

Figure 3: DPPH's radical scavenging activity of aqueous and ethanol root extracts of *Chrysophyllum albidum*. Values are expressed as mean \pm SEM, n = 3. Different lowercase letters represent significant difference between means at $p < 0.05$.

Figure 4: Total antioxidant capacity (TAC) assessment of aqueous and ethanol root extracts of *Chrysophyllum albidum*. Values are expressed as mean \pm SEM, n = 3. Different lowercase letters represent significant difference between means at $p < 0.05$.

The result on proximate analysis of *C. albidum* root samples showed (Table 1) that it contained moisture (41.8mg/g), crude protein (1.20mg/g), crude fibre (30.90mg/g), ash (1.70mg/g), lipid (0.25mg/g), and carbohydrates (24.06mg/g). The moisture values obtained in *C. albidum* root is lower than the values reported for *Delonix regia* root (96.0mg/g), *Daniellia oliveri* stem bark (62.5mg/g), *Carpolobia lutea* root (95.5mg/g), *Moringa oleifera* root (60.6mg/g) and *Piliostig mathonngii* root (83.4mg/g) [22,23]. Moisture content indicates the amount of water present in the material and is very crucial as it serves as benchmark to evaluate the quality and stability (Shelf-life) of food. A lot of biochemical reactions and physiological changes that occur in food are dependent on the moisture content. High moisture content increases biochemical reactions. A variety of factors affect the moisture, content of food and

usually the period and methods of harvesting contributes enormously to the moisture content [22]. The crude protein values obtained in *C. albidum* root is lower than the values reported for in *Balanitesa egyptiaca* root (128.1mg/g), *Moringa oleifera* root (122.5mg/g) and *Delonix regia* root (106.3mg/g) [22,23]. Proteins are polymers of amino acids. Protein acts as enzymes, hormones and antibodies. They maintain fluid, acid and base balance in the body. They also transport substances like oxygen vitamins and minerals to target cells throughout the body. Structural proteins such as collagen and keratin are responsible for the formation of bones, teeth, hair and the outer layer of skin. They help to maintain the structure of blood vessels and other tissues. Amino acids are very crucial for proper functioning of the brain, muscle, and nervous tissue as well as providing the body as a solid

base for physical health. The crude fibre values obtained in *C. albidum* root is lower than the values reported for *Moringa oleifera* root (138mg/g) and *Delonix regia* root (74.4mg/g) [22, 23]. Crude fibres are materials that are indigestible in human and animal organisms. Fibre consumption is regarded as essential because it absorbs water and provides roughage for the bowels, assisting intestinal transit and well normalizes blood lipids thereby reducing cardiovascular disease. It also helps to prevent constipation and decreases blood cholesterol levels. Very low fibre in food is however helpful to digestive processes though it lowers the vitamins and enzyme content of the food material. Higher fibre diet is important for gastro-intestinal health and cholesterol lowering benefits as well as its provision of better results in preventing diverticulosis inflammation. Studies showed that increased fibre content intake of 6g daily among men and women aged 50-70 years was associated with a 25% reduction in ischemic heart disease mortality, independent of calories fat and other dietary variables [22,23,24]. The ash content in *C. albidum* root is lower than that reported in *Moringa oleifera* root (134mg/g) and *Delonix regia* root (93.0mg/g). Ash content is a measure of the total amount of minerals, present within the food substance [22]. The lipid value obtained in *C. albidum* root is lower than the value reported for *Moringa oleifera* root (26.6mg/g) [23]. Lipids are the major components of food as they provide a good source of energy. Fats being made up of hydrogen carbon and oxygen provide essential fatty acids that are not made by the body. Fat makes up about 99% of the lipids fraction of food [23]. The carbohydrate value obtained in *C. albidum* root is lower than the values reported for *Moringa oleifera* root (518.3mg/g) and *Delonix regia* root (901.8mg/g) [22,23]. Carbohydrate in food originates from photosynthesis, an endothermic reductive condensation of CO₂ requiring light energy and chlorophyll pigments. It serves as a source and represents a substantial proportion of the body's energy supply [23].

Mineral analysis showed (Table 2) that *C. albidum* root samples contained sodium, calcium, magnesium, iron, manganese, zinc, potassium and phosphorus at 0.30 mg/g, 8.20 mg/g, 0.96 mg/g, 0.20 mg/g, 0.35mg/g, 1.12mg/g, 13.5mg/g and 11.31mg/g respectively. The sodium value obtained in *C. albidum* root is comparable to the value reported for *Delonix regia* root (0.41mg/g) [22]. Sodium is essential for osmotic equilibrium and body fluid volume as well as in the

transmission of nerve impulses [22]. The calcium value obtained in *C. albidum* root is higher to the value reported for *Delonix regia* root (0.95mg/g). Calcium is required in the formation of strong bones and teeth. Potassium is essential for the regulation of osmotic pressure and pH equilibrium and control of acid alkaline reaction of the blood. Calcium provides animal's bone with rigidity and support [22,23]. The magnesium value obtained in *C. albidum* root is higher to the value reported for *Delonix regia* root (0.14mg/g). Magnesium is required for retention of calcium in teeth and constituents of bones. Magnesium is a key in enzyme activation, magnesium (like calcium) stimulates muscle and nerve irritability (contraction), is involved in the regulation of intracellular acid-base balance, and plays an important role in carbohydrate, protein and lipid metabolism [22, 24]. The iron value obtained in *C. albidum* root is higher to the value reported for *Delonix regia* root (0.01mg/g). Iron is responsible for haemoglobin formation, regulation of the central nervous system and oxidation of protein, fats and carbohydrates [22, 25]. The zinc value obtained in *C. albidum* root is higher to the value reported for *Delonix regia* root (0.07mg/g). Zinc is an active component or cofactor for many important enzyme systems zinc plays a vital role in lipid, protein, and carbohydrate metabolism; being particularly active in the synthesis and metabolism of nucleic acids (RNA) and proteins [22, 26]. The potassium value obtained in *C. albidum* root is quite higher to the value reported for *Delonix regia* root (1.0mg/g). Potassium assists in the regulation of electrolyte, water and acid base in the body and muscle function [22]. The phosphorus value obtained in *C. albidum* root is quite higher to the value reported for *Delonix regia* root (0.4mg/g). Phosphorus helps to filter out waste in the kidneys and plays essential role in the storage and uses of energy in the body [22,26]. Some minerals are structural components (calcium and phosphorus) while others are hemostats (sodium and magnesium) and yet others are component of organic biomolecules (all trace elements such as zinc, iron and so on) [23].

Vitamin C and E (as shown in Table 3) analysis of the root of *C. albidum*. Natural ascorbic acid is very good for the body performance. Lack of ascorbic acid impairs the normal formation of intercellular substances in the body. The clinical manifestation of the deficiency of vitamin C is scurvy. Also vitamin C is required in normal wound healing [27]. Vitamin E is a lipid-soluble, radical trapping antioxidant. The effect of vitamin

E deficiency in experimental animals include testicular atrophy and necrotizing myopathy. Studies have shown that vitamin E also has roles in cell signaling, by inhibition or inactivation of protein kinase C, and in modulation of gene expression, inhibition of cell proliferation, and platelet aggregation. Deficiency of vitamin E is well established in experimental animals, resulting in reproductive failure, necrotizing myopathy, liver and kidney damage, and neurological abnormalities [28].

The qualitative phytochemical screening of aqueous and ethanol root extracts of *C. albidum* revealed the presence of saponins, flavonoids, alkaloids, phenols, terpenoids, xanthoprotein, carbohydrate and tannins. This is comparable as that reported in the leaf, fruit and seed extracts of *C. albidum* by Ojemeke et al. [7], Ademoye et al. [1] and Oputah et al. [29]. These phyto-constituents are reported to confer protective effect on plants against microbial infections or infestation by pests [30]. Also, these secondary metabolites were known to show medicinal activities as well as exhibiting physiological activities [1].

The reducing power (RP), as shown in figure 1, showed no significant difference in the ethanol extract of the root of *C. albidum* and the standard antioxidant used, ascorbic acid. Reducing power of the extracts increases with increase in concentration. However, the reducing power of the ethanol extract is significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) when compared to the aqueous extract. The reducing power of the root of *C. albidum* is higher than that of the fruit of *C. albidum* (0.6nm) as reported by Ademoye et al. [1]. The difference may be due to the different parts used. The reducing capacity of a compound may serve as a significant indicator of its potential antioxidant activity [30].

FRAP assay is a simple, fast and precise assay that measures the total antioxidant power of biological fluids. FRAP assay is reproducible and linearly related to molar concentration of the antioxidant present in the biological sample [30]. Ferric Reducing Antioxidant Potential (FRAP) is an electron transfer assay. The ferric reducing antioxidant potential test is based on the ability of antioxidants present in the test extracts to reduce Fe^{3+} to Fe^{2+} [7]. The ferric reducing antioxidant potential of the aqueous and ethanol extracts of *C. albidum* are comparable to the standard antioxidant used as shown in figure 2. The FRAP

values of the aqueous and ethanol extracts of the root *C. albidum* is comparable to the aqueous extract of *C. albidum* fruit exocarp (0.84 73mg Fe(III)/g extract) as reported Dandare et al. [31]. But its FRAP value of aqueous and ethanol root extract of *C. albidum* is higher than that reported in the fruit pulp and exocarp of the methanol extract (0.79 and 0.72 mg Fe(III)/g extract respectively) and petroleum ether extract (0.70 and 0.62 mg Fe(III)/g extract respectively) [31]. While FRAP value is lower the root extract of *C. albidum* when compared with the FRAP value reported by Ojemeke et al. [7] which is 2.73mg Fe(III)/g extract. This may be due to the different parts used.

DPPH assay combines both hydrogen atom transfer and electron transfer mechanisms [30]. As a rapid and simple measure of antioxidant activity, the DPPH radical scavenging capacity is based on the reduction of the stable radical DPPH to yellow colored diphenylpicrylhydrazine in the presence of a hydrogen donor [7]. The results of the DPPH radical scavenging activities of *C. albidum* aqueous and ethanol extracts are shown in Figure 3. The results showed that there is no significant difference in the radical scavenging capacity of aqueous and ethanol extracts. The results of the DPPH radical scavenging activities of *C. albidum* aqueous and ethanol extracts is higher than that reported by Ojemeke et al. [7] at the same concentration. The difference may be due to the different parts used.

Total antioxidant capacity (TAC) is based on the reduction of Mo(VI) to Mo(V) by antioxidant compounds. The reduction leads to formation of a green phosphate/ molybdate complex which can be measured at 695nm wavelength [7]. The results (as shown in figure 4) indicated that the ethanol extract showed the highest capacity (165.0 mgAAE/extract), compared to the aqueous extract (126.7 mgAAE/extract). The total antioxidant value reported in this study is quite high when compared to the total antioxidant value of *C. albidum* fruit extract (70.36 mgAAE/extract) [1].

4.0 Conclusion

In conclusion, this study revealed that the ethanol root extract of *C. albidum* had better antioxidant activity when compared to the aqueous extracts. This may be attributed to the presence of more bioactive substances ethanol extract than aqueous extract of *C. albidum*. Therefore, the root of *C. albidum* may be employed in the management of

some degenerative diseases caused by oxidative stress. There is need for further investigation of the active compounds responsible for *C. albidum's* activity and its' *in vitro* effect on free radicals. Future research will entail the isolation and characterization of the most active ingredients in root extracts of *C. albidum*.

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6.0 Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

8.0 References

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